

Technology Evidence Base final version

Accompanying document to Deliverable D1.7

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¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

V	Date	Beneficiary/Author	Action
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Summary

In the European Union (EU) Horizon 2020 (H2020) project NextGen, 24 technologies related to circular economy in the water sector were investigated at 10 case studies distributed across Europe. The technologies are involved in water management and recovery, material recovery and energy recovery (Figure 1). In this context, a database containing information and data referring to those technologies was developed. The database is called technology evidence base (TEB), is open access and hosted by Water Europe as part of the Marketplace (<https://mp.watereurope.eu/>).

Figure 1 Circular economy: wastewater is a valuable resource for water, material and energy recovery. It is the nexus between the three cycles, in which the NextGen technologies are involved.

For each technology, a factsheet was elaborated containing the explanation, how this technology works, its unique selling points, requirements to implement the technology, flow schemes, pictures and a link to the case study, in which the technology has been build and applied. For each case study, also a factsheet was elaborated containing the main results such as the performance of the technology, lesson learned from its operation and best practice guidelines as well as the outcome of the assessments such as the life-cycle assessment, life cycle costing and/or risk assessments for human health from recovered water (QMRA) and for the environment from recovered fertilisers (QCRA). In addition, the related legislation is listed which is crucial e.g. to establish the fertiliser on the market. Also contact data of the entities and companies operating those technologies are provided in order to enable consultation

and/or discussion between problem owners and solution providers. The NextGen consortium developed and uploaded 24 technology factsheets (<https://mp.watereurope.eu/teb/>) and 10 case studies factsheets (<https://mp.watereurope.eu/l/CaseStudy/>) including their NextGen results.

After the finalisation of NextGen, the EU H2020 projects ULTIMATE (grant agreement number: 869318) and B-WaterSmart (grant agreement number: 869171) will take over the responsibility for the TEB. They will also collect data and integrate their technologies in the TEB. ULTIMATE plans to add 21 new technologies and will extend the factsheet of 4 already existing technologies. B-WaterSmart is currently preparing a list with technologies they want to add. They will mainly focus on membrane technologies applied for fit-for-purpose water recovery. On the long-term, it is recommended to involve more research and innovation projects to maintain the TEB, because it is time-intensive and needs an expertise to assess the application of new factsheets. Also, via the involvement of those projects, the TEB might remain open access, what is considered as crucial, if a broader spectrum of user types is desired.

The TEB will promote circular economy technologies in the water sector and enable decision makers, engineers, investors and interested persons to gain a fast overview of the innovative technologies available. Hence, the TEB can contribute highly to reach the ambitions of the European Green Deal its Action Plan for Circular Economy to reduce strongly the EU greenhouse gas emissions, to provide clean water, maintain healthy soil, make industry resilient and produce cleaner energy.

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Abbreviations

AAT	Advanced anaerobic technology
AOP	Advanced oxidation processes
AnMBR	Anaerobic membrane bioreactor
ASR	Aquifer storage recovery
CAPEX	Capital expenditures
CEA	Cost-effectiveness analysis
D	Deliverable
ELSAR	Electrostimulated anaerobic reactor
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GAC	Granular activated carbon
H2020	Horizon 2020
HFMC	Hollow fibre membrane contactor
KPI	Key performance indicator
LCA	Life cycle assessment
LCC	Life cycle costing
MBR	Membrane bioreactor
MELiSSA	Micro-ecological life support system alternative
MNR	Metabolic network reactor
OPEX	Operational expenditures
QCRA	Quantitative chemical risk assessment
QMRA	Quantitative microbial risk assessment
RO	Reverse osmosis
SOFC	Solid oxide fuel cell
TEB	Technology evidence base
UF	Ultrafiltration
WP	Work Package
WWTP	Wastewater treatment plant

1. Introduction

The Horizon 2020 project NextGen promotes circular economy technologies based on water recovery, material recovery and energy recovery. At ten case studies distributed across Europe the technologies were conceptualized, designed, constructed and showcased specifically, in Braunschweig (DE), Costa Brava (ES), Westland (NL), Altenrhein (CH), Sernal (UK), La Trappe (NL), Gotland (SE), Athens (EL) and Timișoara (RO) and Filton (UK).

In this frame, a so called Technology Evidence Base (TEB) was established. The TEB is a database that contains and presents generic information on the demonstrated circular economy technologies of NextGen and of two other Horizon 2020 projects, ULTIMATE (GA N° 869318) and B-WaterSmart (GA N° 869474). In addition, the TEB disseminates the case study specific results of each project. The TEB aims to unify the results and to allow for an easy access to relevant information needed for setting up new circular economy schemes in the water sector. The TEB is accessible via the Water Europe Marketplace (*D5.5 The NextGen Online Marketplace*, <https://mp.watereurope.eu/>). For the TEB, the NextGen consortium developed and uploaded 26 technology factsheets (<https://mp.watereurope.eu/teb/>) and 10 case studies factsheets (<https://mp.watereurope.eu/l/CaseStudy/>) including their NextGen results.

While in NextGen the circular economy technologies are mainly applied in the frame municipal wastewater treatment, ULTIMATE focuses on water smart industrial symbioses and demonstrates circular economy based technologies applied in the frame of industrial wastewater treatment. Therefore, ULTIMATE supplements very well the industrial aspect in the TEB and provides new information on symbiotic cooperation opportunities between the industry and the water sector at nine case studies. Furthermore, B-WaterSmart focuses on water smart solutions and management solutions for six coastal cities and regions.

This document accompanies *D1.7 Technology Evidence Base final version* (<https://mp.watereurope.eu/teb/>) and explains the structure and organization of the TEB, it provides information on the content and structure of the technological factsheets, the presentation of the results from NextGen on case study level (<https://mp.watereurope.eu/l/CaseStudy/>) including results from technology performance and lessons learned (WP1, Plana Puig et al. 2022, Kim et al. 2022 and Kleyböcker et al. 2022), results from the assessments (WP2, D2.1 Remy et al. 2022, D.2.2 Misev et al. 2022), legal and regulatory information (WP4) and the link to the Marketplace for business opportunities (WP5, D5.5). This document also outlines the maintenance procedure of the TEB and the future plans for it including aspects regarding the assurance of a good data quality and an extension of the TEB by other projects and solution providers.

2. Structure and organisation of the TEB

The final version of the NextGen parts in the TEB is open accessible via the Water Europe Marketplace at <https://mp.watereurope.eu/> by clicking on the button “Technologies” (Figure 2). Figure 3 illustrates the entrance of the TEB with the three cycles concerning the recovery and reuse of water, material and energy. The nexus between the three cycles shows the potential for synergies of the circular economy technologies and the figure explains the circular economy character of the technologies supporting the TEB users to easily discover new opportunities for creating their own circular economy concepts.

After clicking on one of the cycles, the next webpage provides an overview of the technology domains that are relevant for the selected cycle.

For the water cycle, the subdomains are:

- Wastewater treatment for water reuse
- Rainwater harvesting systems
- Surface water and infiltration systems
- Groundwater systems
- Desalination technologies

For the nutrient and material cycle, the subdomains are:

- Nutrient recovery technologies
- Material recovery technologies
- Food/fodder production technologies

For the energy cycle, the subdomains are:

- Biomass production technologies
- Heat recovery & storage systems

Each technology domain contains subdomains and factsheets as exemplarily shown for the material cycle in Figure 4. By clicking on one of the subdomains, the corresponding factsheets belonging to the certain subdomain are displayed and can be accessed via clicking on them. Furthermore, related case studies are also shown and can be accessed via this pathway.

However, the case study specific factsheet, can also directly be visited by clicking on “case studies” in the left menu on the starting page of the TEB, by clicking on the “Case studies” button on the starting page of the Marketplace or by directly visiting this webpage <https://mp.watereurope.eu/l/CaseStudy/>.

Figure 2 Starting page of the Water Europe Marketplace (D5.5 The NextGen online Marketplace)

The screenshot shows the Water Europe Marketplace interface. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links for 'Login' and 'Sign-up'. A sidebar on the left contains menu items: 'About the Marketplace', 'Technologies', 'Products', 'Case studies', 'Marketplace', 'Events', and 'Networking'. Below the sidebar, a banner reads 'Unlock the full potential of the marketplace' with a 'Login / register' button. The main content area features a central diagram of the 'NEXUS' model, which consists of three interconnected cycles: 'WATER' (blue), 'NUTRIENTS / MATERIAL' (green), and 'ENERGY' (yellow). Each cycle is represented by a circular flow of icons and arrows, with 'WASTE-WATER' acting as a central hub connecting them. Below the diagram, there is a filter section for 'Technologies/Domains: 34' and a grid of technology factsheets. The factsheets include: 'Activated carbon treatment coupled to an AOP', 'Anaerobic Membrane Bioreactor (AnMBR)', 'Biogas production via anaerobic digestion', 'Ammonium sulphate production (air stripping & scrubbing)', 'Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage', 'Bioswale systems', 'Ammonium sulphate production (membrane stripping/ HFMC)', 'Automatic floodgates', and 'Controlled recharge and drainage'.

Figure 3 Entrance to the TEB via the Water Europe Marketplace: showing the three cycles of water, material and energy and corresponding factsheets referring to each domain

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N°776541

The screenshot shows the Water Europe Marketplace interface. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links for 'Login' and 'Sign-up'. A left sidebar contains menu items like 'About the Marketplace', 'Technologies', 'Products', 'Case studies', 'Marketplace', 'Events', and 'Networking'. The main content area displays a circular diagram representing the 'NUTRIENTS / MATERIAL' domain, with arrows indicating a cycle between 'AGRICULTURE', 'INDUSTRY', 'WASTE-WATER', and 'FOOD / FODDER'. To the right of the diagram, a text block states: '5 users are interested in this domain. The demand for fertilizers will increase, since 60% of increase in food production until 2050 will be necessary for keeping up with the growing population (UN, IWA 2019). Taking into account, that the resources for conventional fertilizers are limited and Europe mostly depends on non-European suppliers, alternatives are necessary.' Below this, a 'Subdomains' section lists three categories: 'Nutrient recovery', 'Material recovery technologies', and 'Food/fodder production technologies'. At the bottom, a 'Broader domain' section includes links to 'Resource for Circular Economy' and 'Overview of Technologies'. A 'Related products' section lists 'MobileAR solution for citizen engagement towards CE approach' and 'Digital Easler'. Three factsheet cards are shown with images and titles: 'Ammonium sulphate production (air stripping & scrubbing)', 'Ammonium sulphate production (membrane stripping/ HFMC)', and 'Granulated activated carbon (GAC) production via pyrolysis'. Each card includes a brief description of the technology.

Figure 4 Example for the technology domain of material recovery technologies displaying its subdomains and providing links to its corresponding factsheets

The “Overview of Technologies” can be illustrated by clicking on the corresponding button (Figure 4). Thereby, all factsheets assigned to their subdomains and broader domains can be accessed as shown in Figure 5. This structure is also called *taxonomy of the technologies*.

Figure 5 Overview about the taxonomy of the NextGen technologies: technology domains and subdomains are illustrated in blue and the technology factsheets are coloured in orange

Via the search function in the upper left part of each webpage (Figure 2, Figure 3, Figure 4 and red circle in Figure 6), the user can search directly for a technology or product to be recovered such as biogas, heat, phosphorus, etc.

Below the search function on the right side of the webpage, the green circled “Back to all technologies” button allows to navigate back to the starting page of the TEB.

Figure 6 Technology domain: Energy recovery technologies: red circle shows the “search function” and the green circle indicates the button to navigate back to the starting page of the TEB

Figure 7 shows the technology factsheet. In the upper part (red circle) the pathway of the factsheet is presented. Also, by clicking on the domain or subdomain, the user can navigate back to the overview pages. The same navigation can be done by clicking on the blue button of the broader domain and the orange buttons of the subdomains as shown in Figure 5. Between the different factsheets, links are provided in order to easily switch between pages and to find information (Figure 7, green circle). Those links are further explained in the next paragraph “Content of the factsheets”.

Rapid composting bioreactor

Resource for Circular Economy / Nutrients/Material recovery technol... / Nutrient recovery / Rapid composting bioreactor

Resource for Circular Economy / Nutrients/Material recovery technol... / Material recovery technologies / Rapid composting bioreactor

Unique selling points

- Compost-based eco-engineered media
- Free of enteric pathogens
- Rapid composting: 5-times faster than conventional composting

Description of the technology

Rapid composting can be applied for the treatment of excess sludge together with pruning waste. This technology can be combined with a sewer mining unit containing a membrane bioreactor, in which the excess sludge is produced.

Prior to the rapid composting, the excess sludge is thickened until it reaches a dry solids content of approximately 5%. The wood and green waste is shredded, homogenised and sorted – to get a 2-5 mm fraction by sieving in a pre-treatment step. In a mixing unit, the homogenised wood and green waste is mixed with the thickened excess sludge and an inert filling material consisting of shredded wood of 2-5 cm size. Approximately 700 L/per week are

Broader domains

- Nutrient recovery
- Material recovery technologies
- Overview of Technologies

Related tags

- phosphorus
- potassium
- sludge treatment
- excess sludge
- pruning waste
- green waste
- composte
- humus
- phosphorus recovery

Figure 7 First part of the technology factsheet for the rapid composting bioreactor

3. Content of the factsheets

All technology factsheets have the same structure following the layout in Figure 7 and containing information about the listed categories (see bullet points below). The NextGen consortium discussed and agreed on the structure of the factsheets and Water Europe reviewed and also agreed the concept of the TEB. The basic information is generic and for each category, easy-to-understand with summarised information content is presented together with a link to more detailed information such as literature references. For the cited literature, open access publications shall be the first choice.

Each factsheet contains the following elements:

Technology factsheet with generic information:

- Name of the technology
- Unique selling points
- Description of the technology (point of application, capacity, explanation of the process with literature references, type of product produced by the technology)
- Flow scheme of the technology
- Pictures of the technology and if available short videos
- Synergetic effects and motivation to implement this technology
- Key performance indicators (KPIs) & technical parameters: data for the performance of the technology (e.g. nutrient recovery rate, biogas yield, log removal rate of pathogenic organisms),
- Requirements for the implementation of the technology and operating conditions
- Link to the case study where the technology is applied (here the case study specific information will be presented, see also Figure 8)
- Links to similar related technologies or other technologies producing the same product
- Literature references

The results of the NextGen related technologies are presented as case study specific information in a case study factsheet. This part is accessible via a link at the end of the related technology factsheet, directly via the button “Case studies” on the Marketplace (Figure 2) or on the left hand menu that is always visible when navigating through the Marketplace and TEB.

Case study factsheet with case study specific information (Figure 8):

- Description of the case study
- Applied technologies
- Applied tools
- Abstract of key lessons from WP1 and link to the corresponding deliverables D1.3, D1.4, D1.5 (New approaches and best practices for the optimal operation of the technologies and explaining the success of the symbioses)
- Abstract of the outcomes of the assessments from WP2 in D2.1 (e.g. LCA (CO₂ footprint, energy consumption/production), QMRA, QCRA) and in D2.2 (LCC incl. CAPEX, OPEX, return rate, distribution costs, etc. and CEA),
- Legal and regulatory information regarding the value chain concerning the technology (→link to the corresponding case study results in WP4)

- Contact data of companies/entities operating and assessing the technologies for business opportunities and link to the Marketplace

Case studies

Case studies: 10

Search

Any part of the case study name you are searching for

Countries

Select Countries ...

Countries hosting this case study.

Filter by project

ULTIMATE
 B-WaterSmart
 NextGen

Filter Reset

Altenrhein, Switzerland	Athens, Greece	Braunschweig, Germany
Description	Description	Description
Applied technologies	Applied technologies	Applied technologies
Applied products	Applied products	Technology performance
	Related publications and references	Outcome of assessments
		Legislation
		Applied products

Costa Brava Region, Spain	Filton Airfield, United Kingdom	Gotland, Sweden
Description	Description	Description
Applied technologies	Applied technologies	
Applied products	Applied products	
Related publications and references		

Figure 8 Case studies in the TEB: Braunschweig shows links to the NextGen results such as “Technology performance”, “Outcome of assessments”; “Legislation”; also the factsheets of the technologies in the TEB can be accessed via the shown links

Clicking on the links shown in Figure 8, results in accessing the case study factsheet. Figure 9 shows the upper part of the factsheet. It starts with a picture of the case study, followed by a short description of the case study, the link to the applied technologies, the NextGen results comprising the “technology performance”, the “outcome of the assessments” and “legislation”. There, the main results of the operation of the technologies and their performance are presented in the form of an abstract with a link to a detailed scientific report of the technological work package (WP1). The same has been done for the assessments of the technologies (LCA and risk assessments) in work package 2 under the heading “Outcome of the assessments”.

Related legislation shows the regulations and ordinances which are crucial for the products of the technologies such as the recovered water or material in order to be reused by an end-user.

Because the TEB is part of the Marketplace, the problem owner can be easily use the Marketplace to find a solution provider. In addition, contact persons are assigned to each technology. They can also support and consult problem owners and provide further contact data to their solution providers.

nextGen

Contact data

Contact person
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Involved organisations
 Abwasserverband Braunschweig
 Kompetenzzentrum Wasser Berlin GmbH

Scale ▾

Challenge ▾

Related tags
 biogas struvite ammonia Nutrient recovery Energy recovery

Case study Braunschweig
 Source: AVB

Description

Steinhof, near Braunschweig, has a long tradition of water and nutrient reuse. Already at the end of the 19th century, fields were irrigated with sewage. From 1954 on, the wastewater was mechanically clarified and reused for irrigation. Finally, in 1979, the wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) was built and comprised a conventional activated sludge treatment system and a digestion stage. Until 2016, in summer, the digestate was directly reused in agriculture, while in winter, the digestate was dewatered and stored until the summer season. However, due to the new legislation in Germany, since 2017 only 60% of the digestate can be applied on the fields. The reasons are restricted periods for fertilizing with digested sewage sludge and the limitation of the nitrogen load to the agricultural fields. Thus, the other 40% of the digestate were dewatered and incinerated.

In 2019, a new circular economy concept was implemented. Here, energy recovery technologies are combined with nutrient recovery technologies. Therefore, sludge management concept was adapted to increase the nutrient recovery rate and simultaneously, as a synergetic effect, the biogas recovery rate increased. Hence, circular economy solution comprises a thermal hydrolysis process between two digestion stages and a full-scale nutrient recovery plant consisting of a struvite production unit to recover phosphorus and an ammonium sulphate solution production unit to recover nitrogen. The secondary fertilizers are will be reused by the local farmers and the produced energy in the form of biogas and heat is reused by the plant itself.

Applied technologies

- Enhanced biogas production due to thermal hydrolysis process
- Struvite production
- Ammonium sulphate production stripping scrubbing (air &)

Technology performance and best practices

The goal of the Braunschweig (DE) case study was to enhance biogas production via thermal pressure hydrolysis at the municipal WWTP. Thermal pressure hydrolysis (TRL 9) was performed as a pre-treatment of digestion, resulting in higher biodegradation during digestion. The results showed that the biogas production increased by 20% and the dewatering efficiency of the digestate increased by 10% due to the higher biodegradation of the thermally hydrolysed sludge. Although high attention to operating and maintenance of the system is mandatory, the technical feasibility of the thermal pressure hydrolysis has been successfully demonstrated. The better biodegradation contributed also to an increase in phosphate and ammonium concentrations in the liquor, which are crucial for the subsequent nutrient recovery. Detailed results can be found in D1.4 and in the [case study report](#).

Figure 9 Upper part of the case study factsheet Braunschweig: description of the case study, key lessons: containing an abstract of the main results and providing a link to the detailed report (circled in red)

... for nitrogen removal and recovery, an air stripping and scrubbing unit was implemented to produce ammonium sulphate solution. The recovery rates were easy to control and could be operated between 80% and 97% as required. The potential for the production of $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ solution is 2000 t/a. Detailed results can be found in D1.5 and in the case study report.

Outcome of assessments

The combined sludge and sludge water treatment scheme with thermal pressure hydrolysis, struvite recovery and ammonium sulphate solution recovery is able to recover nutrients with a net-zero CO₂ footprint. Direct N₂O emissions and emissions of reactive nitrogen species are reduced. A further reduction of the CO₂ footprint could be achieved by utilisation of excess heat in summer for the stripper to reduce caustic soda consumption. Further LCA results can be found in D2.1

Legislation and policy recommendations

- DüMV (2012) Verordnung über das Inverkehrbringen von Düngemitteln, Bodenhilfsstoffen, Kultursubstraten und Pflanzenhilfsmitteln (Düngemittelverordnung – DüMV vom 5. Dezember 2012, BGBl. I S. 2482), Bundesministerium der Justiz und Bundesamt für Justiz
- AbwV (2022) Verordnung über Anforderungen an das Einleiten von Abwasser in Gewässer (Abwasserverordnung – AbwV vom 17. Juni 2004 BGBl. I S.1108, 2625 und vom 20. Januar 2022 BGBl. I S. 87, Bundesministerium der Justiz und Bundesamt für Justiz
- EU (2019/1009) Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 laying down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilising products and amending Regulations (EC) No 1069/2009 and (EC) No 1107/2009 and repealing Regulation (EC) No 20
- EU (2021/2086) Commission Delegated Regulation of 5 July 2021 amending Annexes II and IV to Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 of the European Parliament and of the Council for the purpose of adding precipitated phosphate salts and derivatives as a component material category in E

Applied product

NEXTGEN Life Cycle Assessment

Life Cycle Assessment is a standardized framework (ISO 14040) for assessing the potential environmental impacts of a pr...

Publications and references

Project report
NextGen
2022
Kleyböcker, A., Heinze, J., Kraus F.
Technology related results of the case study Braunschweig

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Contact data

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Involved organisations

Abwasserverband Braunschweig
Kompetenzzentrum Wasser Berlin GmbH

Scale ▼

Challenge ▼

Related tags

- biogas
- struvite
- ammonia
- Nutrient recovery
- Energy recovery

Figure 10 Second part of the case study factsheet: example Braunschweig: as soon as D2.1 will be finalised, it will be also available via a link as the case study report is.

4. Future of the TEB

The EU H2020 projects ULTIMATE and B-WaterSmart will take over the responsibility for the TEB after the finalisation of NextGen. Hence, they will extend the TEB with their own technologies, they will maintain the TEB and find a solution together with Water Europe, how to proceed, once they will be finalised, too.

4.1 Integration of other technologies from ULTIMATE and B-WaterSmart

The TEB has been developed as a flexible database and can be extended with additional technologies. Hereby, the domains of the taxonomy (water reuse technologies, material recovery technologies and energy recovery technologies) will remain. However, the subdomains can be adapted, supplemented in the case of new technologies and/or deleted in the case of irrelevant technologies. Hence, the database can be used even beyond the project.

During the lifetime of NextGen, already two other projects started to add their factsheets to the TEB. ULTIMATE is an EU Horizon 2020 funded project (Grant Agreement No. 869318) and started in June 2020. It will last until May 2024. In nine case studies, circular economy concepts for water, material and energy recovery are showcased in the context of water smart industrial symbiosis. ULTIMATE will add 17 additional technologies and contribute to 4 existing technology factsheets. ULTIMATE will take over the responsibility to maintain the TEB after NextGen.

New technologies to be added by ULTIMATE are:

- Electrostimulated anaerobic reactor (ELSAR)
- Immobilised anaerobic high rate anaerobic system (AAT)
- Small bioreactor platform
- Early warning system for membrane fouling (AnMBR)
- Electrodialysis
- Membrane distillation
- Novel tight ultrafiltration (UF) membrane
- Reverse osmosis (RO)
- Adsorption using renewable granular active carbon
- Hydrochar production
- Ammonium adsorption with zeolites
- Coagulation and adsorption with bentonite
- High added value products adsorption and subcritical water extraction
- Monitoring system for high chloride concentrations
- Joint control system for an industrial and a municipal wastewater treatment plant (WWTP)
- Sulphur recovery
- Solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC)

B-WaterSmart is another EU Horizon 2020 project (Grant Agreement No. 869171) and already added six additional case studies to the database. B-WaterSmart deals mainly with water recovery and will mainly contribute the membrane technologies. A list of technologies to be added will be elaborated in the coming weeks.

Furthermore, to gain more scientifically validated data for the TEB, the consortium members of ULTIMATE will promote the TEB and present it to other research projects.

4.2 Maintenance of the TEB

The TEB is and will be hosted by Water Europe. Until now, the projects NextGen and ULTIMATE mainly maintained the TEB. So called data manager were assigned from each project for the domains water recovery, material recovery and energy recovery. Those data managers were responsible to collect the data for the technology factsheets and to upload the project results to the TEB via the case study factsheets.

For the technology factsheets, a review procedure was established, before they were uploaded to the TEB. First the factsheets were prepared by the case study partners who investigated the certain technology and then, reviewed by the corresponding data manager and one scientist of the corresponding project, who had not been involved in the elaboration of the factsheets.

This method will be maintained in the future according to Figure 11. First, the data manager assesses, if the mandatory information and data are provided for a new factsheet or for its update/extension.

Figure 11 Decision tree for accepting a contribution to the TEB

Hereby, mandatory information and data are:

- Classification of the technology group indicating the position of the technology in the infographic and taxonomy
- 3 tags (keywords)
- Unique selling points
- Description of the technology (incl. capacity and level of competence for its operation)
- Flow scheme
- Pictures and (if available) videos
- Synergetic effects and motivation to implement the technology

- Requirements of the technology and operating conditions
- Key performance indicators
- References to case studies or similar projects
- Literature references (including links to publications with DOI, ISBN etc.)

In the case the factsheet exists already, the new contributor uses the already existing factsheet and updates it with his/her own data. The updated factsheet will be shared with the authors of the original factsheet and reviewed by them (in the pdf-version of each factsheet, the authors are indicated). The original authors will have the opportunity to update their contributions in this frame, too. So, they can make sure, that their old data are up to date in the case the technology has been further optimised.

In the case the original authors are not available anymore, a scientist from ULTIMATE or B-WaterSmart will be requested to review the new contribution.

In the case, somebody wants to submit a factsheet who is not a partner of one of the projects, either the data managers suggest a reviewer or another solution has to be found. For those applicants, an online form will be available to submit their contribution.

The case study factsheet are optional to be filled out and contain specific information on:

- Lessons learned from the first implementation and operation of the technology
- Outcome of assessments such as life cycle assessment, cost assessment and risk assessment
- Legal and regulatory information concerning the technology and its products
- Contact data for business opportunities and link to Marketplace

In addition, the data manager will assess the quality of the new contribution via the following aspects:

- **Technology factsheet: data cited in scientific publications?**

Important facts and data must be cited. If the used literature comprises mainly peer reviewed scientific publications, the contribution to the TEB can be accepted, because this indicates good data quality. In this case, the links to the publications and the DOIs or ISBN must be provided in the literature reference section. Therefore, if available, open access publications shall be preferred to cite the facts.

- **Facts and data cited in non-reviewed literature or not cited at all?**

If no peer-reviewed publications were used to cite facts and data, a peer-review process is required to decide, if the contribution can be accepted for publication in the TEB.

In the case, the contribution contains no citation at all, but provides valuable data, a peer review process will help to better assess the quality of the contribution and the suitability for the TEB. The quality of the factsheet depends highly on the reliability of the shown data.

The choice of the reviewers is still under discussion among the core team of the TEB task. In this case, the cooperation with a certain organisation such as the Biorefine Cluster Europe might also be a good option.

In addition, the TEB might also be interesting for technology providers who want to present their technology in the context of the marketplace, but have not done an independent

evaluation or assessment of their technologies by scientific parties. If there is no evidence that the provided data and facts were produced in a reliable way, the contribution can be directly rejected. However, if the evaluator considers the contribution as highly valuable, it can be peer reviewed as well. In the case the reviewer decides to accept the contribution, a label with the statement “data quality is uncertain” has to be implemented.

- **Expiration of a factsheet?**

If there will not be a new update of a certain factsheet within three years, all authors of this factsheet will be automatically asked to update their factsheet otherwise the factsheet will be expire and removed from the TEB. This measure can contribute to keep the TEB up to date. In the case, the authors won't be available anymore after the project lifetimes, an alternative is needed. Different options for the alternative will be discussed in the coming months in the core team of ULTIMATE.

4.3 Potential fate of the TEB after finalisation of ULTIMATE and B-WaterSmart

Currently, different options are being investigated and discussed among the core team of the TEB task. For example, one option might be to involve other organisations such as the Biorefine Cluster Europe. ULTIMATE recently joined the cluster (<https://www.biorefine.eu/>), which aims to interconnect bio-based research and innovation projects dealing with circular economy and to disseminate and promote their results.

This will be further discussed with the final version of the TEB in order to show to potential candidates a first complete version of the TEB and not only a concept.

After the project lifetimes, the next data managers will be appointed. They can be members of collaborating research projects or refer to connected organisations such as the Biorefine Cluster Europe. This has to be elaborated and discussed in detail in the coming weeks in ULTIMATE.

5. Conclusion

The TEB is a valuable database for interested persons, engineers, decision makers and investors, for gaining a fast overview on circular economy related technologies in the water sector. It provides easy to understand information on the functionality of the technologies, but also in-depth data on the performance of the technologies, their CO₂-footprint, their costs and legislative framework.

The TEB can highly contribute to the transition from a linear to a circular economy in Europe and via its close connection to the Marketplace, it might even serve as an initial spark for problem owners to find the right solution provider and to initiate first contacts to entities or institutions that can provide valuable experience reports and lessons learned for certain technologies.

Its maintenance is important and time-intensive. Also, expert knowledge is beneficial to update the TEB and take care of a good data quality. Therefore, it is recommended to further cooperate with research projects to integrate further innovative technologies and update the already existing concepts with potential future improvements. In this way, the open access to the TEB might also be maintained, which is an important aspect to address a wider spectrum of users.

6. Literature references

- Kim et al. (2022). New approaches and best practices for closing the energy cycle in the water sector, D1.4 NextGen Gant Agreement Number 776541.
- Kleyböcker, A., Kenyeres, I., Poór-pocsi, E., Nättorp, A. Loreggian, L., Schaub, M., Egli, C., Grozavescu, M., Murariu, M., Radu, B., Scheer, P., Lindeboom, R., Giurgiu, R. Plata Rios, C., Suters, R., Heinze, J., Soares, A., Vale, P., Kim, J., Lanham, A., Hofman, J. (2022). New approaches and best practices for closing the materials cycle in the water sector, D1.5 NextGen Gant Agreement Number 776541. 204 p.
- Nättorp, A., Misev, V. (2022). Economic assessment and cost efficiency analysis of NextGen demo case solutions, D2.2 NextGen Grant Agreement Number 776541, 87 p.
- Plana Puig et al. (2022). New approaches and best practices for closing the water cycle in the water sector, D1.3 NextGen Gant Agreement Number 776541.
- Remy, C., Kraus, F., Conzelmann, L., Seis, W., Zamzow, M. (2022). Environmental life cycle assessment and risk analysis of NextGen demo case solutions. D2.1 NextGen Grant Agreement Number 776541, 195 p.

